

Obtaining the Tsallis Distribution from $e_i/T \ll 1$ and $e_i/T \gg 1$ Considerations? Part 2

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. March 18, 2025

In previous notes (1), we have argued that in the Shannon, Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases all follow from considerations of $-e_i/T$ information. In particular, all three derivations may begin with the notion of a function F such that $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, where $p(e_i)$ is an unnormalized probability. Interestingly, the entropy function is then: $\sum_i p_1(e_i) F(p_1(e_i))$ for the Shannon and Kaniadakis cases and $\sum_i p_1(e_i)^q F(p_1(e_i))$ for the Tsallis, where $p_1(e_i)$ is normalized.

In Part I, we noted that Tsallis entropy could be obtained from considerations based on $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ for $e_i/T \ll 1$. Here, we show that Kaniadakis entropy also follows from $e_i/T \ll 1$ considerations. In both cases, one models $F(p)$ by a single parameter power of $p(e_i)$. The Tsallis case only uses $p(e_i)$ power b , while the Kaniadakis case allows for $p(e_i)$ power b together with $p(e_i)$ power $-b$. In other words, this approach leads to at least two F functions and two entropies, each characterized by a parameter, Tsallis (q), Kaniadakis (k) such that $q=1$ or $k=0$ yields $F = \ln$, i.e. the Shannon result. The key idea seems to be that the linear term $-e_i/T$ is automatically linked with $\exp(-e_i/T)$ for $e_i/T \ll 1$ and $\exp(q \ln(b))$ is, in turn, associated with a power law b power q .

Information Based on $-e_i/T$

We suggest that the Shannon, Tsallis and Kaniadakis cases are strongly linked to the notion of the information $-e_i/T$. In fact, all three make use of the notion:

$$F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T \quad ((1)) \quad \text{where } p(e_i) \text{ is an unnormalized probability}$$

In the Shannon case: $F(p) = \ln(p)$,

in the Tsallis, $F(p) = \ln_q(p) = \{p(e_i)^{1-q} - 1\} / \{1-q\}$

and in the Kaniadakis case, $\ln_k(p) = 1/(2k) \{p^k - p^{-k}\}$.

For $q=1$ or $k=0$, one retrieves $\ln(p)$, i.e. the Shannon result, by using l'Hopital's rule.

Here, as in Part I, we consider ((1)) with respect to $e_i/T \ll 1$.

$e_i/T \ll 1$ Limit Power Expansion

In the case of $e_i/T \ll 1$, one may consider a power law expansion of ((1)), i.e.

$$F(p) = C + ap + bpp + cppp + \dots \quad ((2))$$

In such a case, one has many powers of p If one restricts oneself to a single parameter for power, presumably based on experimental results, then:

$$F(p) \text{ is linked to } p^b \text{ and/or } p^{-b} \quad ((3))$$

The goal is then to have $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$.

To link the linear $-e_i/T$ to a power law with a single parameter, one may first link it to an exponential.

$$\exp(-e_i/T) \approx 1 - e_i/T \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Secondly: } p^b = \exp(b \ln(p)) \quad ((5))$$

One may combine ((4)) and ((5)) to obtain $-e_i/T$ very readily in two ways:

$$((7a)) \quad \{ \exp(b(-e_i/T)) - 1 \} / b = -e_i/T = F(p) \text{ in the } e_i/T \ll 1 \text{ limit and}$$

$$((8)) \quad \{ \exp(b(-e_i/T)) - \exp(-b(-e_i/T)) \} / (2b) = F(p) \text{ in the } e_i/T \ll 1 \text{ limit}$$

There does not seem to be any reason to prefer one over the other at this point.

We next check whether both ((7)) and ((8)) may yield \ln , i.e. Shannon's result, under a certain value of b , namely $b=0$.

$$\text{Shannon's result is: } F(p) = \ln(p) = -e_i/T \text{ so } p(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)$$

One may associate then $-e_i/T$ in the exponentials of ((7)) and ((8)) with $\ln(p)$ in the $b=0$ limit. This suggests that:

$$((7b)) \quad (p^b - 1) / b = F(p) \text{ in general and}$$

$$((8b)) \quad \{ p^b - p^{-b} \} / (2b) = F(p) \text{ in general}$$

((7b)) may be called the Tsallis case with $b=1-q$, i.e. a new parameter q is introduced so that $q=1$ yields $b=0$, i.e. the Shannon result

((8b)) may be called the Kaniadakis case with b being renamed as k .

Given ((7b)) and ((8b)), one may find unnormalized $p(e_i)$ functions such that $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, i.e.

$$\text{Tsallis } \exp_q(e_i) = \{ 1 - (1-q)e_i/T \}^{1/(1-q)} \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{Kaniadakis } \exp_k(e_i) = \{ \sqrt{1+k^2 e_i^2} + k e_i \}^{1/k} \quad ((10))$$

We note here that $p(e_i)$ is an unnormalized probability as are $\exp q$ and $\exp k$. This leads to the question: What does one do with normalized probabilities? We try to address this in the section after the next.

Discussion

Tsallis and Kaniadakis $F(p)$ functions are quite different and yet both are immediate solutions of the single parameter power law of p fitting of $F(p)$. (One may of course try to argue against a single parameter power law, but this is a simple result which may match experiment and seems worth pursuing.) In this context, both the Tsallis and Kaniadakis approaches are candidates which yield different distributions.

We suggest in addition, that there seems to be a fundamental difference in the way that one calculates e_i power n moments in both cases.

For the Tsallis case: $\ln q(p) = \{ \text{Sum over } i \ p(e_i)^{\text{power } (1-q) - 1} \} / (1-q)$

Given that $p(e_i)^{\text{power } (1-q)}$ is only linked with q (and not $-k$, k as in the Kaniadakis case), it is tempting to consider the Tsallis case as one in which $p(e_i)^{\text{power } b-1}$ replaces $p(e_i)$ as the probability weight. This idea is considered in more detail in the next section.

In the Kaniadakis case, $p(e_i)^{\text{power } k}$ and $p(e_i)^{\text{power } -k}$ appear and so there is no notion of a single $p(e_i)^{\text{power } b-1}$ representing a probability weight. In such a case, the probability weight may very well still be $p(e_i)$. Again, we consider this notion in the next section.

The Notion of Entropy

In the above section, we suggested that the Tsallis and Kaniadakis schemes both emerge from the definition: $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, $F(p(e_i))$ linked with a single parameter power of p and $e_i/T \ll 1$. We, however, used $p(e_i)$ as an unnormalized probability distribution. In general, however, one deals with normalized $p(e_i)$, which we call $p_1(e_i)$.

We note that one may formally create an entropy function by using a kind of probability weight multiplied by $F(p_1(e_i))$. This function may then be extremized subject to a first order e_i moment and $\text{Sum over } i \ p_1(e_i) = 1$. The question becomes: What probability weight is needed such that ((9)) and ((10)) are obtained?

For the Tsallis case, one finds that:

$$S(\text{Tsallis}) = \{ \text{Sum over } i \ p_1(e_i)^{\text{power } q - 1} \} / \{1-q\} \quad ((11))$$

If one uses $p_1(e_i)^{\text{power } q}$ as the probability weight, with the constraint $\text{Sum over } i \ e_i \ p_1(e_i)^{\text{power } q} = 1$, then one may extremize replacing p_1 with $p(e_i)$ and set the Lagrange multiplier of the

e_i moment to $-1/T$ and the Lagrange multiplier of $\sum_i p_1(e_i)$ to 1 to obtain the unnormalized ((9)). The unnormalized probability may be obtained from using the entropy extremization procedure, just as in the Shannon case. We have suggested in previous notes that one may bypass the notion of extremization subject to constraints and use an $-e_i/T$ information approach which holds for all e_i power n moments.

In the Kaniadakis case, one may use: $1/(2k) \sum_i \{ p(e_i)^k - p(e_i)^{-k} \}$ ((12))

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Shannon, Tsallis and Kaniadakis scenarios may all begin with the notion: $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, where $p(e_i)$ is an unnormalized probability distribution. We suggest seeking single parameter (which may be both positive and negative) power of $p(e_i)$ solutions to $F(p(e_i))$ and examine the $e_i/T \ll 1$ case because a linear $-e_i/T$ is immediately linked to $\exp(-e_i/T)$ and a power law $p(e_i)^b$, to $\exp(b \ln(p))$. We thus show that for a single parameter scenario, one may use $p(e_i)^b$ yielding the Tsallis case, or $p(e_i)^{-b}$ with $p(e_i)^{-b}$, yielding the Tsallis case. In other words, both cases arise together in this approach.

We then consider the notion of an entropy function and extremization and associate the Tsallis case with a probability weight $p(e_i)^q$ whereas the Kaniadakis case still uses $p(e_i)$. We show that for $q=1$ (Tsallis) and $k=0$ (Kaniadakis), one obtains the usual Shannon's result $F(p) = \ln(p)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Information ($-e_i/T$) Method and Kaniadakis Entropy (preprint, zenodo, 2025)